

REPRESENTATION OF WOMEN IN INDIAN CLASSICS

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Abstract:

In literary works of western literature Women were frequently the topic of interest for writers. Literature makes it clear that women social roles were more constrained than the roles of men. And since men composed the vast majority of early works, misogyny tends to taint much of it. Women were attributed with such negative traits like deceit, selfishness, seduction and temptation. They were always controlled, exploited and restrained and depicted in literature as submissive, docile, objects of desire, shameful and lower to their male counterparts. On the other hand in Indian classics, Women were not given any importance in family or society but they were the source of spiritual support and base of hero's strength and society's strength in general. With her own nobility and profound human affection, the women were able to stimulate action and hero's aspirations. The common traits of women in ancient Indian literature included their kindness and generosity, persistence and patience, love, loyalty, and desire for happiness. These traits are regarded as "the golden rule," the defining feature of Indian culture, and a never-ending source of inspiration for Indian art and literature. The representation of women's external as well as internal beauty in regard to social issues like caste, marriage and religion according to the Dharma concept always glorified and honoured by people of India.

Key Words: Indian Classics, Women, Ancient, Representation

Introduction:

Classical studies is a vast field comprises of the study of languages, literature, history, art and philosophy and culture of the ancient world. It spans a wide range of academic fields like history, archaeology, art, literature, philosophy and it also involves the study of ancient texts and relics. This field of study could be very useful for the one who wants to understand the roots of our culture and for those who simply wants to learn about our ancient and influential civilization of the world. The term Indian classical studies refers to the written works composed in Sanskrit, Pali and Prakrit languages and produced in the Indian subcontinent, which includes modern day Indian, Pakistan, Bangladesh and Nepal. This literature consists of variety of genres and themes like religious texts, poetry, epics, plays and prose and covers over two thousand years of history.

Sanskrit literature is regarded as the oldest and the most influential of the Indian classical literatures, with a legacy of poetry, drama, philosophical and scientific treatises. The Vedas, which are regarded as the highly sacred texts of Hinduism, are included in the earliest Sanskrit literature, which dates back to the Vedic period (c.1500-500 BCE). The *Ramayana*, The *Mahabharata* and the plays of Kalidasa are notable examples of Sanskrit literature. Indian classical literature continues to play a significant role in the cultural heritage of the Indian subcontinent and has had significant impact on the literary and cultural traditions of the region and beyond.

India is one of the earliest cradles of Indian civilization and its culture is immense, mysterious and compassionate. The three components that make up this culture are religion, philosophy and art with religion serving as the inspiration for majority of literature. Traditional Indian literature is the reflection of all Indian set of beliefs in the art of language with its "distinctive feature is the humanity" displayed in literary works through character portrayal, which is "special means of art to reflect objective reality". (Thuy 658) The Indian literature has a legacy of thousands of years with special accomplishments becoming the common spiritual heritage of mankind in the process of constant movement of development of world literature. Literature got deeply influenced by the society and it is a mirror image of the culture in which it is written. We could learn from our past and adapt it in our present as our culture.

The Vedas or ancient scriptures skilfully describe women as being both a complement and a supplement to their male counterparts. Four names come to mind when we talk about notable women of our Vedic era- Ghosha, Lopamudra, Maitreyi and Gargi. These women portrayal became the base which influenced and inspires poets, who then use their poetry and lyrics to create the characters for women. However the way in which ideas were conceived and how the characters were depicted varies from one person to another. A patriarchal society's requirements were taken into consideration in the creation and modification of characters. The epics *Ramayana* and the *Mahabharata* are two prime examples of these in which portrayal of women characters and traits of Sita and Draupadi varies from each other. Earlier one being the most devoted wife, submissive and sacrificing still she was thrown out of her kingdom without any fault of her own and latter one was courageous, always spoke

her mind, intelligent and considered to be the first feminist of Hindu mythology and still she was blamed for the war, the Mahabharata which was fought between Pandavs and Kauravs.

In the epic Ramayana, many minor characters are sidelined by writers like Kaikeyi, Mandodari, Tara and Sita's character is not acknowledged much despite the main character of the epic. Sita was the daughter of King Janak, a great Rajrishi and Queen Sunaina of Mithila. As said by Valmiki in his epic Ramayana, that their relationship of father and daughter was under appreciated and it was not by chance. Sita was also a sage in her own right as she was very well educated and has great confidence in her power of observation. Readers and writers always misunderstood her traits and decisions to be meek, hesitant and not courageous at all. On the contrary she was very intelligent, observant, confident in her every decision, she chose for herself when she has to speak and when to keep quiet. It does not mean that decision was burdened on her but she took all her decision after proper evaluation of the whole situation. It was her decision to accompany Ram in his exile despite of everyone's disagreement, it was her decision to give the agnipariksha because she knew that Ram has full trust on her but it was for justification in the eyes of the people. She was a dutiful wife, loving, caring, obedient and sacrificial one but by her own choice and without Sita, her husband's traits his skill, loyalty, love and valour could never have come through.

Kaikeyi- She was the only daughter among eight children of King Ashvapati of Kekaya. She was raised among men where males needs, their egos, decisions and emotions were valued. Despite being raised in such environment she was always overshadowed by her siblings achievements still she was grew up in a well educated, courageous and compassionate woman who was known for her impenitent and fearless attitude. She got married to King Dashrath when he was hunting in Kashmir and instantly fall in love with her. Their marriage was permitted by King Ashvapati on one condition that Kaikeyi's son will be the King of Ayodhya and it was the first instance when first vow was broken and forgotten by Dashrath and it lead his downfall. She was a fierce warrior who fought alongside of her husband, first incidence when a woman fought in a battlefield. She saved Dashrath by riding the chariot wheel with her little finger and showed her mental willpower and physical strength in the war. Despite being the educated woman, a fierce warrior, a doting wife and boldest queen of the three, she was portrayed as the heartless villain who destroys her own family peace and happiness. It is still not decided that she was the pawn in the bigger scheme of things or her story was a fruit of negative emotions or the creation of circumstances.

Mandodari- She was the daughter of aapsara Hema and raised by her father Mayasura, King of Asuras. She was raised like Kaikeyi with men around her, her two brothers and father. She was always be the sensible one among all three and taught her brothers to not fight with each other but to support each other. She was raised with lot of affection and protection from her father's side and she was a remarkable woman who was counted as one of Panchakanyas of Hinduism, along with Tara, Draupadi, Kunti, Ahlya. She got married to Raavan but she got to know about his disloyalty and arrogance after marriage. She was always being the pillar of strength for her husband but never encourages him and warns him against his wrongdoing. She was the embodiment of silent strength and wisdom and her love for Raavan was unconditional but not blind.

Tara- She was married to King Vali, though her birth is debatable some says she was the daughter of Sushena, monkey physician and some says she was an apsara came out from sea when amritmanthan was done. She was very well aware of Vali's flaws like Mandodari and loved him unconditionally. She always gave advice from time to time as she was the moral compass of her husband and supported him. She saved Sugriva's life by constant guiding and helps Vali to see beyond his anger and got promise from him to not kill his brother.

In the epic Mahabharata, there are many female characters who were powerful enough but not influential one like Satyawati, Hidimba, Uloopi, Kunti etc. Firstly we discuss Satyawati who was the most powerful, cunning and astute female. She was the daughter of a fisherman and made her way to the queen of Hastinapur with her own conditions. She was the mother of the famous sage, Veda Vyasa from a Rishi Parashara while she was ferrying him across Yamuna. She had similarity with Kaikeyi as she was blunt and honest but soft and kind as well. She married Shantanu, King of Hastinapur on a condition that her own sons will rule the kingdom not his son Devvrat. But her dream was not fulfilled and her sons died without any heir to rule. She was never got afraid before bending any rules for her own advantage and not before making new rules as well. She is a mixture of both the traits, as she was praised for her farsightedness, shrewdness, expertise in politics and diplomacy but criticized for her over ambitious nature and the ways she took to reach those heights of ambitions. Uloopi- was the Naga princess and the daughter of the Naga King Kauravya. She got married to Arjuna when he was on twelve years exile and had a son with him called Iravan. After some time living with Arjuna, he left to complete his exile period and forgot her. While passing from Manipur, he got married another princess Chitrangada, with her his another son born called Bhabruvahana. Uloopi's selflessness was her primary characteristic which was not easy to find in anyone. She saved Arjuna's life and raised his two sons to be skilled warriors like him and provide him power to breathe underwater and understand the language of marine animals. Kunti- She was the daughter of King Surasena, born as Pritha but given to King's childless cousin King Kuntibhoja who raised with lot of affection. She got married to King Pandu in her swayamvar and came to Hastinapur after sometime Pandu marries another princess Maitri and Kunti treated her with lot of affection like

a sister. Kunti is criticized because of many reasons such as she abandoned her own son Karna and revealed him his reality when she felt right to use him for his own sons protection and when she said to divide Draupadi among themselves without turning back to look what is being divided. She was the strong matriarch of the family whose words will not go in vain and she was being wise, mature and determined after her husband died in woods as she had to raise her five sons alone. She secured her sons right and return to Hastinapur with her sons and always portrayed as the most affectionate and devoted mother.

Draupadi- She was always depicted as the most powerful, vengeful and most controversial female of our history who always speaks her mind and never got afraid before stood up against anyone. She was the princess of Panchal and daughter of King Drupad hence known as Panchali and Draupadi. She was engaged to Arjuna as he won the swayamvar but when his mother uttered her words to divide what they brought among all that changed the course of history. She got married to five brothers and sacrificed her love which was only for Arjuna and now divided among all five of her husband. She faced the humiliation in Hastinapur court where she was being disrobed by Kauravs but saved by Krishna where she was being transformed as her heart only wants vengeance for this huge insult. Despite all the complexity of her character she still is the most influential and powerful woman of all times.

In the play *Abhigyan Shakuntalam*, written by the greatest playwright and poet, Kalidasa. This play is about a beautiful young lady Shakuntala, entire play revolves around her. She is the daughter of Rishi Vishwamitra and apsara Menaka and lived in the ashram of Rishi Kanva. Her character portrayal by the playwright was the most ideal one throughout the play. She was being depicted as the epitome of chastity, patience, beauty, grace and sacrifice. She was so beautiful that when Dushyanta saw her, he instantly fallen in love and both got married in ashram. She was not only beautiful but skillful and argumentative also when she reached to her husband palace where he denied her identification then tried to convince him through many arguments and incidents that she is his wife. Despite all this she did not lose her patience and lived in forest for seven years and raised her son alone. She was the ideal character like Sita and Savitri and her strength lies in her powerful emotions.

Conclusion:

It is clear that all these women were ahead of their time in some way or another, be it their presence of mind or quality to sacrifice. There are many themes which are common in all stories like compassion, patience, courage, endurance and determination. All these characters are discarded the idea that women should being quiet and silently suffered all their lives in fact they all broke all conventions and left a lasting impact in the stories of their lives. With all their positive traits these women deserve to be the representatives of ancient Indian women and ancient Indian culture

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